

QUESTIONNAIRE OF PERCEPTION AND DETECTION OF COMPETENCIES (QPDC)

- To which Operational Unit do you belong?

- Please indicate your professional qualification:

A - TECHNICAL PROFESSIONAL SKILLS - *I believe I possess the technical and professional knowledge necessary to do my job*

A - TECHNICAL PROFESSIONAL SKILLS - *I have mastered the techniques, protocols, and procedures necessary to perform my work*

A - TECHNICAL PROFESSIONAL SKILLS - *Sometimes I realize that there are technical-professional areas on which I would need to increase my skills to do my job better*

B- ORGANIZATIONAL SKILLS - *I am able to organize my work activity by giving myself priorities*

B- ORGANIZATIONAL SKILLS - *I am able to meet deadlines for activities and projects, regularly monitoring actions and timelines*

B- ORGANIZATIONAL SKILLS - *I am able to achieve set goals even in complex work situations, always maintaining more than satisfactory work standards and redefining the plan of action if necessary*

C- RELATIONAL-COMMUNICATIONAL SKILLS - *I am able to circulate information, ideas and new knowledge that I have and make it available to my work group*

C- RELATIONAL-COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS - *I am able to develop different approaches and modes of communication depending on people and circumstances*

C- RELATIONAL-COMMUNICATIONAL SKILLS - *I am able to contain and reflect on emotions and impulses such as anger, aggression and frustration*

D - INEXPRESSED SKILLS/ATTITUDES - *I believe I possess skills/attitudes that are not required of my job profile but could be made available to the organization in which I work*

D - UNEXPRESSED SKILLS/APTITUDES - *Indicate unexpressed skills/aptitudes that you believe you possess:*

1. *Creativity; capacity for vision and contamination*
2. *Process approach, data processing and database*
3. *Planning of activities*
4. *Digital solutions, production/operational process analysis (all possibly if necessary shared with the working group, but you can always improve)*
5. *Management of histologic material for Clinical Trials, from request to preparation of material c/o Pathologic Anatomy, Morgagni Hospital, Forli*
6. *Rapid assessment of priorities*
7. *Previous experience in Institutional Relations, Networking actions, Internationalization. Active listening skills and empathy that could be used to develop coaching and teambuilding activities*
8. *logistical/organizational skills*
9. *Ability to be a team player, project management*
10. *Relational empathy; drafting and close monitoring of rules and procedures*
11. *I enjoy working in the area of quality; I have no specific skills, but would like to have them in the area of statistics and data analysis*
12. *I have successfully completed a non-university Level I online master's degree in psycho-neuro-endocrine-immunology*
13. *Practical biotechnology and biological analysis skills*
14. *Knowledge of pharmaceutical chemistry, general knowledge of my bachelor's degree in pharmaceutical chemistry and technology*
15. *Motivation, team working, problem solving skills, aptitude for working in groups*
16. *Specialty in urology*
17. *specialty in oncology, empathy*

18. *Organizational skills, creativity, ideas for marketing*
19. *Skills in teaching on Scientific English Writing and Image Editing*
20. *Excellent writing skills*
21. *Problem solving and ability to create group and consistent with my skills also to become a reference point of the group and for the group. Despite some difficult moments, I "live" my work with enthusiasm and passion. I would like more to make my experience and knowledge (also learned from the master's degrees I have done) available to train/guide the lab workers toward constant management of quality culture. Working in "quality," means not only managing bureaucracy but improving the quality of everyday work. To do a good job you need to plan it, monitor it, improve it over time; it is unthinkable that you can do it all, only at inspection/audit visits etc...*
22. *Difficult in one line... for example pragmatism, organization, reliability*
23. *Bachelor's degree*
24. *Relationship with the public and institutions*
25. *Ability to communicate and manage intra team relationships, project management skills. Ability to create events, social network management to network and visibility to profiles.*
26. *project management*
27. *Analytical approach including business, contracting, analysis of complex scenarios, training skills*
28. *Ability to create and maintain relationships*
29. *Outreach/relational approach*
30. *Organizational skills*

E - PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE EVALUATION - *Do you think it might be useful to develop a system for mapping and evaluating competencies?*

E - ASSESSMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE - *I am aware of the current level of my skills (self-assessment)*

E - ASSESSMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE - *I happen to discuss with my Manager about the current level of my skills and the level that is expected of me (skills to be increased for the purpose of my professional development)*

E - PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE EVALUATION - *Do you feel that the results of the current and expected skills assessment can be useful for your professional development pathway?*

F - INDIVIDUAL AND GROUP DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY - *I am aware of my professional contribution within the Group of which I am a member*

F - INDIVIDUAL AND GROUP DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY - *My professional growth path within the Group of which I am a member was outlined*

G - ORGANIZATION AND SKILL DEVELOPMENT - *My organization gives me the opportunity to increase my skills (technical-professional, organizational, relational communicative)*

G - ORGANIZATION AND SKILL DEVELOPMENT- *My organization invests in people, including through appropriate training*

• **Indicate educational events/topics you would like to participate in during 2024**

- 1) *Training events related to pulmonary pathology and also more technical events related to technologies adopted in diagnostics and data interpretation*
- 2) *International congresses*
- 3) *Training on new procurement code ; work psychology; stress load management*
- 4) *Graphics for production of communication materials, conflict management*
- 5) *English course, course on variant classification and events on new methodologies/panels to be used in molecular diagnostics*
- 6) *Team building, communication, problem solving, update clinical management of solid tumor cell therapies (e.g. toxicity management).*
- 7) *Problem solving, team building*
- 8) *Congresses related to advanced therapies, quality assurance courses*
- 9) *Resource optimization, management*
- 10) *Patient communication courses, team building, masters in PV*
- 11) *Problem solving, communication with colleagues and cancer patient, English language enhancement, statistics*
- 12) *Congresses/Meetings regarding Next Generation Sequencing and related platforms*
- 13) *Responsible Expert course, master's degree in undergraduate Economics and Management in Healthcare, master's degree in undergraduate Physical and Technological Basis of Hadrontherapy and*
- 14) *Precision radiotherapy*
- 15) *Territorial services*
- 16) *Machine Learning in Oncology*
- 17) *English, qualitative patient perception assessment surveys.*
- 18) *Patient engagement - PROMS and PREMS - project management – leadership*
- 19) *English*
- 20) *SEO skills development, English course, improvement comptencies Adobe package management, topics related to fundraising*

- 21) *Team building*
- 22) *Courses on chemical and biological hazards related to laboratories; other courses on MAPO; technical courses on gases and laboratory fume hoods; other technical courses on hazards in the Institute.*
- 23) *English (speaking) course and basic course for genomics and transcriptomics data analysis*
- 24) *Genomic and transcriptomic data analysis*
- 25) *National and international events related to my professional activities*
- 26) *Insights on Quality Management System, courses from internal auditor, courses to learn more about aspects of ISO15189 and other issues that may arise from the entry into force of REGULATION (EU) 2017/746 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices*
- 27) *extrahospital pathways - pressure injuries - emergency management in the operating unit*
- 28) *Artificial intelligence and machine learning*
- 29) *Uro-oncology and transplantation meetings*
- 30) *Do not have specific skills, but I would like to have them in the field of statistics and data analysis*
- 31) *EANM 2024*
- 32) *Genomics: Master Omics Data Analysis (University of Padua); hematology: ASH, EHA*
- 33) *training courses inherent to clinical research (practical, legislative, modelling and statistical processing aspects), refresher courses on oncological issues with medical-nuclear intersection, refresher courses in tomographic/medical-nuclear radiology area*
- 34) *International conferences and workshops on the zebrafish model*
- 35) *Team building, organizational issues*
- 36) *Risk analysis in health care; organizational models in health care*
- 37) *Conferences and training workshops*
- 38) *Business intelligence, artificial intelligence, SAS statistical techniques update, project management*
- 39) *English course / medication*
- 40) *I would like to sharpen my skills in bioinformatics and data analysis.*
- 41) *GISMA conference GISCI conference GISCOR conference.*
- 42) *Training for use of tools, meet the professor*
- 43) *Workshops on molecular immunology, conferences on immunotherapies and CAR T therapy*
- 44) *ASCO*
- 45) *Meeting on manufacturing of ATMP*
- 46) *Project management*
- 47) *Master magnetic resonance imaging and events related to it*
- 48) *Dressings, psychology,*
- 49) *Relational, team building, importance of job serenity*
- 50) *new organizational models*
- 51) *In-depth training course privacy topic/training courses useful for investigative analysis phase studies.*
- 52) *Developing leadership and management skills, Skills mapping and analysis, Measuring the impact of training, Effective communication, Organizational well-being*

53) Course on Public Speaking, Conflict Management, Coaching

54) Clinical ethics

55) ESMO

56) Managerial/entrepreneurial; management

57) Prevention and safety

58) Problem solving, communication with colleagues and the cancer patient, English language enhancement, statistics